

SPYNOTE – Dangerous and Powerful Remote Controller for Android

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Abstract-- SpyNote is an Android remote access trojan (RAT) that was leaked on malware discussion forums in mid-2016. SpyNote can update itself, download and install new apps, read SMS messages, access the phone's last GPS location, listen to and record audio from the device's microphone, access the video camera, listen to calls, make calls, retrieve contact lists, and access technical information such as the device's IMEI number, WiFi MAC address, and carrier details.

SpyNote is a tool for exploiting Android phones and gaining total remote control of the device. Simply designed graphical user interface is used for the working build yourself a customized apk for injecting payload. In August 03,2016 SpyNote introduced.

Moreover this paper shows how can hack the android and iOS devices in different network with route port forwarding. Currently SpyNote support the connection with android devices. And also my research indicates that, we can decrypt data from application's backup files

Keywords — SpyNote, Android Phones, Payload, Route Port forwarding.

I. INTRODUCTION:

SpyNote is recognised as the best android rat because it has the capacity to hack any Android devices. It also features a simple user interface that allows users to utilise it quickly. Furthermore, this programme has the ability to hijack the front or primary camera in real time. Hacking is made easy using this programme. This software can hack android latest version even android pie.

SpyNote is a java-based client/server application. For the client, Android is used, and the server is written in Java/Swing. Once installed, the application icon is removed from the victim's device. SpyNote is unique as it does not need root access to the device in order to obtain these capabilities. SpyNote version 2 allows users to build their own version of the RAT that can communicate with C2 servers configured during the building process. Though SpyNote has not yet been seen in active attacks, Palo Alto Networks expects cybercriminals to begin using it since the builder for SpyNote is freely available.

Features

- Access the device's storage and modify, view or delete files.
- Use the SMS app to read and write messages.
- Use the phone to initiate calls, modify call logs or access and collect contacts.
- Record photo or video footage with available cameras silently.
- Use the microphone to record what is happening around the phone.
- Activate and track the GPS sensor. Modify installed applications.
- Acquire software and hardware details.
- Operators get access to a 'FUN PANEL' that can be used to manipulate the phone's behavior in weird and unexpected ways.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Buthaina Mohammed AL-Zadjali at el [1] The Android platform is a popular open source smartphone operating system. With a wide range of applications, Android's use and adaption is fast rising. It also gives developers unrestricted access to and modification of source code. Because of the open nature of the Android platform, attackers are enticed to engage in a variety of illicit activities. Android users are likely to instal and download a large number of apps that may include dangerous code supplied by software hackers. The goal of this article is to investigate the Android Operating System's most serious security threats and vulnerabilities.

Praful Meshram at el [2] Smartphones, although offering a range of services that are necessary in our everyday lives, such as SMS, calls, cameras, Bluetooth, GPS, and other apps, are also portable computers. Android smartphones are becoming increasingly popular as a result of their appealing features. Understanding the best practises for Android security has never been more vital, given its growing popularity and reputation as one of the most dominant players in the mobile industry. The Android operating system has a reputation for being hackable. The different hazards and security concerns that Activity, Broadcast Receivers, and Content Providers represent are discussed in this article, as well as how they might be accountable for sensitive data leaks without the user's awareness. It also describes the different assaults and their preventative mechanisms, with a focus on the YASSE preventative mechanism. This study also discusses a variety of alternative cloud-based security methodologies and technologies that not only improve device security but also reduce device system burden.

Karthik S at el [3] Android apps may access user data, system data, device data, and other Smartphone resources via a permission-based manner. The Android application's permissions must be declared by the developer. For the Android application to be installed successfully, the user must approve certain permissions. These are declarations of permissions. If the user grants rights at the time of installation, the app can access resources and information at any time. It doesn't need to ask for permissions again. Because of its security flaws, the Android operating system is vulnerable to a variety of security threats.

Taenam Cho at el [4] Smartphones are more than just phones; they are also portable computers that provide a variety of services such as calls, messages, emails, GPS, camera, Wi-Fi, and Bluetooth applications. These apps store and handle a variety of internal data as well as sensitive personal information like address books. Smartphones allow for quick and easy data transfer across 3G, 4G, and WiFi. As a result, personal data kept on Smartphones is vulnerable to leaking. Content Providers, which are used by Android to transfer data

across apps, are particularly vulnerable to unauthorised data leaking. The current research examines the vulnerabilities of Content Providers and uses a rogue software to demonstrate the hazards involved.

G. Delac at el [5] The rise of smart-phone devices with ever-improving technical capabilities has raised the issue of mobile device security. Because of considerable advancements in both hardware and operating systems, mobile devices are quickly becoming appealing targets for malicious assaults. Modern mobile platforms, such as Android, iOS, and Symbian, are becoming more and more like classic PC operating systems. As a result, the issues of maintaining smart-phone security are beginning to resemble those of PC platforms. Smartphones may be infected with worms, trojan horses, and other virus families if malicious material is installed, compromising the security and privacy of the user, or even taking complete control of the device. Because of developments in mobile network technology, such malicious information may quickly propagate thanks to smart-phones' capacity to maintain a persistent Internet connection across 3G or Wi-Fi networks..

III. PROBLEM DEFENITONS

Firstly, download this tool. Need to turn off the system firewall and security to unzip the file downloaded. When unzipping finished, just run the application. To use this program, you must have Java installed on your computer. You may also download Java if you don't already have it installed on your computer.

Fig:1 The SpyNote file is shown. When you open this file, it will prompt you for the port number and password.

Fig 1

Fig:2 is the interface. Simply enter your port number (1337) in the port no. field, turn on the reception option, and then click the Generate apk button. If Java is already installed or available on the machine, just run the SpyNote file to access the interface.

fig:2

Generate Payload following by Tool>Build APK. Enter the needful details and set a DNS to make wide area network connection and provide a testing port number to make connection establishment. Also the tool provide an option to bind with an existing application to hide the generated payload.

fig : 3

fig : 4

Here's where you made your apk file. The spying Microsoft Apk file may be found in the same folder as the programme. Simply use social engineering to transfer this file to the victim's device. and then install it on the victim's device (fig 5)

fig: 5

When the victim clicks this button choice after successfully installing the application, you will successfully receive your victim's session on your machine. Now, in the tool, choose Device to check where you obtained the victim's device. (See Figure 6)

fig: 6

Simply right-click on the device and a slew of choices will appear, all of which you may utilise.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Current version of SpyNote provide the connection is only with android and not support any application management. But hacker can see the list of installed applications on the victim's device. It is possible to connect iOS with the help of SpyNote and ngrok. And also can access some backup files of installed application by backup files.

V. RESULT

The hacked device is in WAN (Wide Area Network) and the victim can not identify the system because the route port forwarding is enabled. Hacker can easily capture the picture, accessing file manager, decrypt application messages etc from android or iOS

VI. CONCLUSION

Analysis of the SpyNote sample indicates that the threat actors behind the surveillance campaign had extensive control over victims' devices. Not only does this piece of malware have considerable features, but it is also highly customizable to evade detection and deceive victims into downloading, installing, and providing full access to their devices. Given this, it's hardly surprising that the opponent was able to maintain control of the campaign for more than

a decade.

It is also obvious that users should be taught not to download mobile apps from unofficial app shops. Furthermore, Device Administrator privileges should only be given to trusted programmes, if at all.

VII. REFERENCES

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